

The structure of barium phosphate glasses and its influence on their thermodynamic stability and viscous flow

Rajesh Dagupati^{a,*}, Marek Liška^b, Alberto López-Grande^c, Francisco Muñoz^{c,**}

^a FunGlass, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50, Trenčín, Slovakia

^b VILA-Joint Glass Centre of the IIC SAS, TnUAD, And FChPT STU, Alexander Dubček University of Trenčín, Študentská 2, SK-911 50, Trenčín, Slovakia

^c Institute of Ceramics and Glass (CSIC), Kelsen 5, 28049, Madrid, Spain

HIGHLIGHTS

- A refined application of the SVTD model has been developed for BaO–P₂O₅ glasses.
- Short structure and properties of BaO–P₂O₅ glasses estimated from SVTD model.
- The activation energy of viscous flow in the equilibrium melts and in the undercooled liquids has been discussed.

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ABSTRACT

The Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva thermodynamic (SVTD) model of associated solutions has been developed in glasses of the system BaO–P₂O₅, with the aim of deriving their short range structure and predicting the volume properties. The applicability of the model was examined by comparing the structure obtained from thermodynamic modelling and by Nuclear Magnetic Resonance spectroscopy. The evaluation of the molar volume of the investigated glasses was carried out through comparison of the experimental values calculated by two approaches: i) with the glass molar volume obtained through a linear combination of the product of the molar fractions of system components and their respective crystalline volume; and ii) with the molar volumes calculated by a multilinear regression analysis of the experimental molar volume of each composition. Furthermore, the viscosity curves were determined at low and high temperature ranges by beam-bending and rotation methods from which the fragility and activation energy of the viscous flow have been calculated and correlated with the thermodynamic chemical structure of the glasses.

1. Introduction

Accurate knowledge of glasses as a function of their composition is indispensable to material science and glass chemistry in particular [1–5] in order to measure/predict their macroscopic properties. In order to establish the relationship between the composition, structure and physical properties in amorphous materials, researchers utilized sensitive and robust tools such as solid-state Magic Angle Spinning Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (MAS-NMR), neutron diffraction, extended X-ray absorption fine structure, and Raman or Fourier Transform infrared spectroscopies. In addition, researchers have developed distinct theoretical models, such as Simon's approximation [6], Conradt's model [7], the ideal associated solutions model [8], and CALPHAD method [9] etc.

These models have been used to predict the structure via the estimation of the type of structural units (short-range order) and associates (medium-range order), which are responsible for the changes in properties that can be observed experimentally with respect to their composition.

Among the various models employed, the ideal associated solutions model does not need the use of adjustable parameters. This model was first developed in glasses by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva on the basis of the rigorous approach of De Donder and has proven its validity for the systems formed from any number of components with different chemical nature [10–13]. There have been several investigations based on this model that aimed at establishing the composition-structure-property relationships in various other glass systems [14–17]. For instance,

* Corresponding author.

** Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: rajesh.dagupati@tuni.sk (R. Dagupati), fmunoz@icv.csic.es (F. Muñoz).

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Chromčková et al. [14] applied this model to calcium phosphate glasses to describe their structure by quantifying the phosphate tetrahedral units (Q^3 , Q^2 and Q^1) and compared with units obtained from Nuclear Magnetic Resonance results. In sodium borosilicate glasses, Vedishcheva et al. [15] were able to quantify both borate and silicate basic structural units in the cuts with $x_{Na_2O}/x_{B_2O_3} = 1$, $x_{Si_2O}/x_{B_2O_3} = 1$, and $x_{Na_2O} = 0.2$ and verified the accuracy of the model through comparison with available experimental measurements. The structure of glasses of the system $Na_2O-CaO-MgO-SiO_2$ has also been examined by Chromčková et al. [16] through the combination of Raman spectroscopy and thermodynamic modelling and the validation of the model was tested by comparing the number of independent components obtained from the model and analysis of Raman spectra of the glasses using the Principle Component Analysis procedure. Finally, Hruška et al. [17] have recently investigated the structure of $Na_2O-B_2O_3$ glasses against the Na_2O content through the SVTD model and also established its relationship with the high-temperature Raman spectroscopy data.

Hruška et al. [18] have also recently constructed the associated solutions model in the system $BaO-P_2O_5$ but did not taken into account the structure of stable crystalline phase $3BaO \cdot 2P_2O_5$ (B3P2) that exists in the $BaO-P_2O_5$ equilibrium phase diagram [19] for which there is no data about its Gibbs function. They have verified the model applicability by comparing the Raman spectra of system components that can be obtained through the analysis of the Raman spectra of the glasses by multivariate curve resolution and Malfait's decomposition [20,21]. In this work, however, we will present an improved thermodynamic model that has been reconstructed for $BaO-P_2O_5$ glass system after including the crystalline phase $3BaO \cdot 2P_2O_5$ phase (B3P2) and quantified the tetrahedral units Q^n ($n = 0, 1, 2$ and 3) against the BaO content. To prove this new approximation, a series of glasses were prepared and characterized by MAS-NMR spectroscopy. The partial molar volumes of the system components were estimated by multi-linear regression analysis of the experimentally determined molar volumes of the studied glasses and then compared with the molar volumes of the crystalline phases. Furthermore, the viscosity of selected glasses in the system was measured at low and high temperatures, and the kinetic fragility and viscous flow activation energy correlated with the structure of the glasses.

2. Experimental

2.1. Glass melting and characterization

A series of binary barium phosphate glasses with chemical composition $xBaO-(100-x)P_2O_5$ ($x = 40, 42.5, 45, 47.5, 50, 52.5, 55, \text{ and } 57.5$ mol.%) were prepared by melting and quenching technique. Batches of 100 g were prepared by mixing analytical grade purity ammonium dihydrogen phosphate ($NH_4H_2PO_4$) and barium carbonate ($BaCO_3$) as precursors. The batches were calcined in alumina crucibles, up to 700 °C with slow heating for 12 h, then melted in between 1100 °C and 1250 °C for 2 h, depending on the barium content. Alumina crucibles were used in order to avoid the high corrosion that can take place when using Pt based crucibles at high temperatures and the likely high dissolution of SiO_2 into the melts in case of using silica or porcelain crucibles. The alumina crucible that the melts were poured onto preheated (300 °C) brass moulds and annealed for 2 h at a temperature approximately 5 °C below the glass transition temperature, T_g , to release the thermal stresses. X-ray diffraction patterns were obtained in a Bruker D8 Advance diffractometer in the range $10 \leq 2\theta \leq 80^\circ$ with a step size of 0.02° and 1 s acquisition for each step. The chemical composition of the glasses was analysed by X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy by a Bruker S8 Tiger spectrometer using pressed pellets by mixing 0.3 g of powdered glass and 5.5 g of $Li_2B_4O_7$.

The T_g and coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) were determined from the thermal expansion curves of the glasses measured in air using a Netzsch Gerätebau model 420 PC/1 dilatometer with a heating rate of 5

$K \text{ min}^{-1}$.

^{31}P MAS-NMR spectroscopy was performed on a Bruker ASX 400 spectrometer operating at 161.96 MHz (9.4 T) with pulse length 2.5 μs and 60s delay time; spinning rate 10 kHz. Chemical shifts are relative to 85% H_3PO_4 solution at 0 ppm and error in its determination is taken as ± 1 ppm. The ^{31}P MAS-NMR spectra, including spinning side bands, were simulated using *dmfit* software [22] to obtain values regarding the parameters like isotropic chemical shifts, line widths (FWHM) and relative content of different Q^n species.

The viscosity was determined at high and low temperatures by rotation and beam-bending viscometers, respectively [23]. A high-temperature Haake viscometer of the cylindrical Searle type (Haake, Karlsruhe, Germany) was used to measure the viscosity between 10^3-10^1 dPa s and using rotation speeds of 5–15 rpm over 12 min. Three measurements were taken for each temperature with three different variable rotation speeds between 5 and 15 rpm. To measure the viscosity within the $10^{12.5}-10^9$ dPa s range, a VIS401 (Bähr Thermoanalyse, Germany) viscometer with a 40 mm open span in symmetric three-point mode was employed. Glass beams were heated at 2 K min^{-1} using weights of 100 g and 200 g.

The density of samples, ρ , was determined as the average of three measurements using Archimedes principle and ethanol (0.861 g cm^{-3} at 20 °C) as the buoyancy liquid. The index of refraction of the samples was also measured at wavelength 589.3 nm (the sodium D line) using an Abbe refractometer and monobromonaphthalene as contact liquid.

2.2. Thermodynamic model of associated solutions

According to this model, oxide glasses are formed from ideal solutions whose constituents are the salt-like products formed by the chemical reactions of pure oxides, and unreacted oxides, the salt-like products having the same stoichiometry as the crystalline compounds that exist in the equilibrium phase diagram of the corresponding compositional system.

For the state of the ideal solution, the total Gibbs energy can be expressed as

$$G(n_1, n_2, \dots, n_N) = \sum_{i=1}^N n_i G_{m,i} + RT \sum_{i=1}^N n_i \ln \left(\frac{n_i}{\sum_{j=1}^N n_j} \right) \quad (1)$$

where T is the system temperature, N is the number of species, n_i is the molar amount of i th species, and $G_{m,i}$ is the molar Gibbs energy of pure i th species at temperature and pressure of the system. T_g is used as system temperature for thermodynamic models of glass.

Eq. (1) is a characteristic equation of the system, so all thermodynamic properties can be calculated from it.

The molar Gibbs energies, listed in the database as FACT [24], of the crystalline compounds, are used as input parameters, as the short-range order of the model salt-like products and these crystalline phases is similar.

In order to calculate the equilibrium system composition, the Gibbs free energy of the system must be minimized, keeping the overall system composition with respect to the molar amount of each system species [25].

The associated solutions model for $BaO-P_2O_5$ glasses has been constructed through the theory developed by Shakhmatkin and Vedishcheva in the following way. The phase diagram regarding the $BaO-P_2O_5$ glasses adapted from ref. [19] and in which five stable crystalline compounds are identified: $4BaO \cdot P_2O_5$ (B4P), $3BaO \cdot P_2O_5$ (B3P), $2BaO \cdot P_2O_5$ (B2P), $BaO \cdot P_2O_5$ (BP), $3BaO \cdot 2P_2O_5$ (B3P2). The crystalline compound, $BaO \cdot 2P_2O_5$ (BP2) does not exist in the phase diagram but is available in FACT data base and has also been taken into account.

The Gibbs energy of each compound was taken from the FACT data base, except B3P2 compound. The value of the B3P2 component, was

Fig. 5. Experimental and calculated molar volume (V_m) a) Multi-linear regression analysis, and b) SVTD model for BaO–P₂O₅ glasses against BaO content. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

was used:

$$V_m = \frac{\sum L_i V_i}{1.661K} \quad (9)$$

where K is coefficient of cell filling taken as 0.5 roughly in the present case because it is a reasonable estimation for crystals with unknown structure; V_i is an ionic volume of an element ($4/3\pi R_i^3$ with R_i being ionic radii); L_i is a stoichiometric number of element i in nominal formula of the component. For instance, in Ba₃P₄O₁₃ (B3P2) component, the L_i for Ba, P and O elements is 3, 4 and 13, respectively. Thus, the molar volume of the glasses of the corresponding compositions has been calculated from the molar volumes of the crystalline compounds and the equilibrium molar amounts of the system components. Fig. 5b now shows the molar volume calculated with the SVTD model along with the experimental molar volume against the analysed BaO content. Additionally, the inset in Fig. 5b represents the molar free volume of the glasses as calculated in the following way:

$$V_{\text{free}} = V_m - \sum_i x_i v_i \quad (10)$$

where $v_i = 4/3 \pi N_a \left[(j r_a^3 + k r_o^3) / 3 \right]$ for $A_j O_k$ oxide compound; r_a and r_o

are the ionic radii.

The V_{free} of the glasses also decreases with BaO content, in the same way as the experimental molar volume and that calculated by the thermodynamic approach.

The determined viscosity has been depicted in Fig. 6 for glasses with 40 and 45 mol % BaO in a) and for 50–57.5 mol % compositions in b); and all data points have been fitted to the following Vogel-Fulcher-Tammann (VFT) equation;

$$\eta = \eta_0 \exp\left(\frac{B}{T - T_0}\right) \quad (11)$$

where B and T_0 are constants, and T is the absolute temperature.

Fig. 7a shows the plots of $\log \eta$ against T_g/T , from which the kinetic fragility of the glasses has been determined at their T_g values. The variation of fragility with composition is also represented in Fig. 7b, showing an increase with the BaO content in agreement with an increased depolymerisation of the glass network with the increase of the modifier content.

The activation energy (E_a) of viscous flow of the melts and under-cooled liquids has also been calculated for selected compositions (40, 45, 50, 52.5, 55 and 57.5 mol % BaO) from the linear regression analysis of the plots of $\ln \eta$ against the inverse temperature ($1/T$), as depicted in

Fig. 6. VFT fitting temperature dependent viscosity a) 40, 45 mol% BaO, and b) 50, 52.5, 55, 57.5 mol% for BaO–P₂O₅ glasses against BaO content. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 8. Linear regression analysis of the plots of $\ln \eta$ against the inverse temperature ($1/T$) for BaO–P₂O₅ glasses. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

zinc for a constant P₂O₅ content; and more recently Xia et al. [34] have shown that the fragility of metaphosphate glasses can be correlated with the strength of cross-linking of the phosphate chains that build up the network. In that sense, glasses where the bonds between modifier and oxygens are weaker will have a higher fragility, while glasses with strong modifier to oxygen bonds will show lower fragilities. In the case of the results presented here for the same modifier cation, the networks with a smaller number of P–O–P bonds will thus experience a higher fragility, as is shown in the increase of m with the BaO content. On the other hand, the analysis of the activation energy for the viscous flow of the equilibrium and undercooled liquids may allow a further understanding of the evolution of the structure upon cooling and the resultant glass that is obtained from melts of different composition.

The activation energy of the melts above the liquidus temperature of each composition decreases with the barium content increase in the glasses, which is in accordance with the fact that this activation energy depends on the number of covalent bonds to be formed; therefore, the lower the number of P–O–P bonds that should be formed in the glass network, the lower the activation energy of the viscous flow in the corresponding liquid. This is also, because in the polyphosphate region of composition, > 50 mol % BaO, the number of interconnecting points between phosphate chains becomes much smaller, as the length of the chains decreases, the effect on the activation energy is enhanced with respect to the observed decrease in the ultraphosphate glasses below 50 mol % BaO.

However, as can be seen in Fig. 8 for compositions between 52.5 and

57.5% BaO, there are two regions of different slope from which two activation energy values can be obtained. The temperatures at which the slope changes (852 °C, 971 °C, and 1141 °C) would correspond to the liquidus temperatures in the equilibrium phase diagram (Fig. 9) at the transition between the liquid in equilibrium and the metastable state of each glass forming melt. Below these temperatures, the liquid will be in equilibrium with the Ba₃P₄O₁₃ phase for the 52.5 and 55 mol % BaO compositions and with Ba₂P₂O₇ at temperatures above 983 °C. Then, between 83 °C and 850 °C, the liquid is in equilibrium with Ba₃P₄O₁₃. The increase of the activation energy of the viscosity between the metaphosphate glass and the one with 55 mol % BaO is interpreted as a consequence of an increased ordering of the liquid that would give rise to crystallization of Ba₃P₄O₁₃ at a later stage. As one goes from 50 to 55 mol % BaO, the relative content of liquid in equilibrium with the Ba₃P₄O₁₃ phase will progressively be reduced and so producing such an increase in the viscous flow activation energy. Furthermore, the liquid will also contain less BaO than the original melt from which it comes, so contributing to the increase of the activation energy.

At the 57.5 mol % BaO, however, the liquid will undergo first the domain of the equilibrium between the Ba₂P₂O₇ and the liquid, giving rise to a different modification of the composition and content of the liquid in equilibrium with that phase. This composition actually produces crystallization of Ba₂P₂O₇ upon cooling the melt, as it can be seen in the XRD pattern Fig. S1 of supplementary information, although viscosity measurements of the undercooled liquid were allowed down to about 875 °C before crystallization started.

Fig. 9. a) Melt, and b) under cooled liquid activation energy for BaO–P₂O₅ glasses against BaO content. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

The approach of using the SVTD modelling allowed us to obtain the structural speciation of the glasses based on the known structures of the crystalline phases of the corresponding equilibrium phase diagram and, furthermore, one can also obtain valuable information on the thermodynamic stability through the calculation of the total Gibbs free energy of the system under study. Some representative results are shown in Fig. 10-a, where the total G value of the BaO–P₂O₅ system has been plotted against the BaO molar content in the 40–55 mol % range, as calculated at several constant temperatures between 1000 °C and 1200 °C. On the one hand, it can be clearly seen that the thermodynamic stability of the system decreases with the increase of the BaO content.

Fig. 10. a) G values for BaO contents between 40 and 55 mol % and temperatures between 1000 °C and 1200 °C; b) plot of the number of NBO per phosphorus for the same range of BaO contents as calculated from the S–V thermodynamic model. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

This can actually be correlated with the own structure of the glasses in terms of the non-bridging oxygens content for each composition, which is represented as NBO/P ratio as a function of the same BaO content in Fig. 10-b. The increase of the barium in the system gives rise to an overall linear increase of the amount of non-bridging oxygens, which results in a lower thermodynamic stability of the system. On the other side, the stability of the liquids increases with the increase in temperature which is reflected in the decrease of the G value for all compositions.

Additionally, one may also calculate the variation of the G function with temperature for each composition, which is represented in Fig. 11 for the same range of temperatures. The derivative of G with respect to T at constant p is actually the entropy of the system with opposite sign. The value of entropy decreases with the content of barium for any temperature, meaning that the order of the system is higher at higher BaO contents. Furthermore, the entropy increases with the increase in temperature due to the higher disorder of the system. This indicates that the compositions of the liquid with higher barium contents have a higher tendency toward crystallization. Even though the decrease of entropy does not follow a linear behaviour within the ranges of barium contents and temperatures, as it shows a change of slope at about the metaphosphate composition (50 mol % BaO), the decreasing values of entropy with the content of BaO can be linked to the fact that the viscosity of the melts presents a change of slope with the decrease of temperature. As it was seen in Fig. 8 for compositions between 50 and 57.5 mol %

Fig. 11. Derivative of G, as a function of composition, for temperatures between 1025 °C and 1200 °C and BaO contents between 40 and 55 mol %. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

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